

Geological Insights from Seismic Refraction in the South Thomson Orogen: A Comparative Study of Delay-Time, Plus-Minus, and GRM Methods

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ABSTRACT

The South Thomson Project was initiated to enhance the understanding of the geology and mineral potential of the South Thomson Orogen. One approach the South Thomson Project is utilizing to advance this knowledge is by gathering seismic refraction data at 16 selected locations to evaluate cover thickness (i.e., the distribution of lithology and sedimentary basin layers over the underlying geological structures). Seismic refraction data was acquired using a typical linear array with 48 geophones and a 40 kg drop weight as the energy source. Cover thickness estimates were derived from refracted data using Delay-time, plus-minus, and GRM techniques. This led to the extraction of a three-layer model, which was interpreted separately for each method. Numerical results demonstrate that GRM outperform the others, by providing more accurate estimation on subsurface features.

KEYWORDS: SOUTHERN THOMSON PROJECT, SEISMIC REFRACTION, DELAY-TIME, PLUS-MINUS, GRM.

1- INTRODUCTION

The Thomson Orogen of eastern Australia covers ~1,000,000 km² but is poorly understood and underexplored due to extensive sedimentary layer that in places reaches thicknesses of 4 km (Henderson et al., 2020). This has necessitated a reliance on geophysical datasets to advance our understanding of this region and its relationships within the broader Tasmanides of eastern (Burton, 2010; Roach et al., 2015). The Thomson Orogen is an inferred Paleozoic orogen in the north-east of Australia that is interpreted to extend across northwestern New South Wales, northeastern South Australia, southeastern Northern Territory and much of central Queensland (Goodwin et al., 2016). The Thomson Orogen has an inferred spatial extent of ~1,150,000 km² of which only ~15,500 km² (~1.4%) exists as outcrop (Raymond et al., 2018).

The vast majority of the orogen is concealed beneath more recent sedimentary basins (some up to several kilometers thick) and regolith cover. Consequently, the Thomson Orogen is one of the least understood regions in Australia's geology, with its mineral potential similarly poorly comprehended. The Southern Thomson Project is a joint initiative between Geoscience Australia, the Geological Survey of New South Wales, and the Geological Survey of Queensland. This project targets the southern Thomson Orogen (Scatter map of the project illustrated in Figure 1) with the goal of enhancing the understanding of the basement geology, cover sequences, and mineral potential in the region, thereby lowering the risk of undercover greenfields exploration by identifying areas with potential for mineral exploration (Goodwin et al., 2016).

To address this issue, a drill 16 stratigraphic boreholes was proposed to collect samples of the basement geology that can be comprehensively analysed to improve the understanding of the geological evolution of this region. To reduce the uncertainty associated with intersecting the target stratigraphy at each of the borehole sites, Estimating the thickness of the cover using refraction seismic geophysical techniques was one of the tasks that was done before drilling. The focus of this article is on the seismic refraction technique and the use of three methods Delay-time, Plus-minus and GRM to interpret the data related to the NAN2 site in Australia.

2- METHOD AND RESULTS

The Seismic refraction interpretation methods involve analyzing the travel times of seismic waves to deduce subsurface geological structures. These methods are commonly used in geophysical surveys to estimate the depths, velocities, and characteristics of underground layers (Mussett et al., 2000). Over the last several decades, the applications of seismic-refraction techniques have evolved from larger-scale investigations (e.g., earthquakes, seismotectonics, oil/gas, etc.) to

smaller-scale surveys. Seismic refraction techniques analyze how seismic waves behave when they encounter subsurface interfaces. The primary focus is on compressional (P) waves due to their ease of identification and ability to pass through all liquids and solids. Seismic refraction data were collected at NAN2 site using a conventional linear array consisting of four cables, with a total of 48 geophones spaced 5 meters apart, resulting in a 235-meter spread. Two Geometrics Geodes (master and slave units) converted the geophone (Longet LGT 4.5 Hz) signals to a laptop running Seismodule Controller Software. The P-wave seismic source was produced by a Propelled Energy Generator (R.T. Clarke Companies, Inc. PEG-40), which uses an elastomer band to launch a 40 kg weight onto an impact plate. Multiple weight drops were stacked to form a single record, with recording automatically triggered by a sensor on the impact plate (Goodwin et al., 2016).

There are several methods for interpreting seismic refraction data, each useful depending on the geological conditions and the level of detail required. The data of the NAN2 site were interpreted by three methods: Delay-time, Plus-minus and Generalized Reciprocal Method (GRM), which are respectively described in each of these methods and their results.

2-1- Delay-Time Method

The Delay-Time method is the basis for most refraction interpretation techniques and one of the simplest approaches for determining the subsurface geometry beneath each geophone in seismic refraction surveys. It allows for the precise calculation of the velocity of the second layer and the average velocity of the first layer using intermediate shot points. This method also facilitates the determination of the depth of the fracture boundary directly below each geophone (Geldart & Sheriff, 2004). Delay time is not an observable quantity, but is a function of the depth to a refracting horizon and of the velocities of propagation along the refractor and through the overlying media. The intercept time associated with a refracted wave is composed of two delay times, one at the energy source and the other at the detector (K. M. Barry, 1967).

To avoid overcrowding and irregularities in the resulting time-distance graph, we exclude distant shots, reducing the dataset to 7 shots. These include 3 middle shots, 2 initial shots, and 2 final distant shots, using shots 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. By analyzing the slope of the graph at each shot location, we determine the velocity range for the first layer (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Time-Distance plot of NAN2 profile data.

In the Delay-Time method, the result is accurate only within the overlapping zone of the refracted waves from the initial and final shots. Outside this range, the method does not hold true (Figure 2). To calculate T' at the location of each geophone, we first compute $T_{AP} - T_{BP}$ for each geophone. Then, using the time-distance graph, we determine the reciprocal time T_{AB} . Finally T' is obtained using the equation (1):

$$T' = \frac{T_{AB}}{2} + \frac{(T_{AP} - T_{BP})}{2} \quad (1)$$

By plotting the T' - X diagram, a line is obtained whose slope is equal to the velocity of the second layer (Figure 3). The slope of the line from the equation of the dotted line is 0.4674 that yielding a second layer velocity of 2170.413 m/s.

Figure 2: overlapping zone of the refracted waves.

Figure 3: The T'-X diagram shows a line representing the second layer's velocity.

With the value of T' at each geophone location, the velocity of the second layer, and the distance, we can easily calculate D_{TP} at each geophone using the equation (2). Once D_{TP} is known, the thickness of the refractor surface at each geophone location is calculated using the equation (3):

$$D_{TP} = T'_{AP} - \frac{X}{V_2} \quad (2)$$

$$h_p = \frac{D_{TP} V_1}{\cos(\sin^{-1}(\frac{V_1}{V_2}))} \quad (3)$$

By utilizing the velocities of the first and second layers, we can calculate the thickness of the first layer beneath each geophone, providing the actual geometry of the refractor surface (Figure 4).

2-2- Plus-Minus Method

The plus-minus method, also known as CRMT that improves upon the delay-time method by allowing for lateral variations in subsurface conditions, such as variations in refractor depth or velocity. In fact this method, can be used to determine the velocity of the second layer and the geometry of the refractor beneath each geophone (J. Hagedoorn, 1959). Similar to the Delay-Time method, its accuracy is confined to the overlapping zone of refracted waves from the initial and final shots, and it is not applicable beyond this zone. In the plus-minus method, the near surface is modeled as a layer above a halfspace where both the layer and the halfspace are allowed to have varying velocities. The method is based on the analysis of the so-called 'plus time' T_D^+ and 'minus time' T_D^- that are given by (Yilmaz, 2001):

$$T_D^+ = T_{AD} + T_{HD} - T_{AH} \quad (4a)$$

$$T_D^- = T_{AD} - T_{HD} - T_{AH} \quad (4b)$$

Once the T_D^- value is obtained for each geophone, the ΔT_D^- value is determined at intervals of $2\Delta X$. This allows us to calculate the velocity of the second layer using the equation (5):

$$\Delta T_D^- = \frac{2(\Delta X)}{V_2} \quad (5)$$

Next, the T_D^+ value is set equal to T_D^- , enabling us to calculate the depth of the refractor surface for each geophone through the equation (6):

$$Z_D = \frac{T_D^+ V_1 V_2}{2\sqrt{V_2^2 - V_1^2}} \quad (6)$$

After determining the velocities of the first and second layers, the thickness of the first layer beneath each geophone is calculated. Using the geophones' height coordinates, the actual refractor surface geometry is derived (Figure 5).

Figure 4 : The figure illustrates the cross section of Delay-time.

Figure 5 : The figure illustrates the cross section of Plus-minus.

2-3- Generalized Reciprocal Method (GRM)

The Generalized Reciprocal Method (GRM) is an important technique in seismic interpretation, particularly useful for analyzing refraction data. This method, first introduced by Palmer, differs fundamentally from the delay-time and plus-minus methods. While the latter provides the velocity of a segment along the line, the GRM focuses on individual points, similar to reflection seismic techniques. By using this approach, the precise velocity at a specific point in the second layer can be determined. By analyzing the reciprocal relationship between wave velocity and time, we can infer subsurface structures (Palmer, 1981). In this method, the first parameter to be calculated is T_v , which is essential for velocity analysis. It is determined using the equation (7):

$$T_v = \frac{T_{AY} - T_{BX} + T_{AB}}{2} \quad (7)$$

For velocity analysis, we seek an optimal XY distance, where XY has the highest likelihood of reflecting the received seismic wave from a point on the refracting surface at the critical refraction angle. To find this optimal XY , several potential XY are tested, and their corresponding T_v values are calculated. A T_v -Offset-AG graph is then plotted, and the optimal XY is identified from the graph. Offset-AG represents the distance between the shot point at the start of the profile and point G (shown as red in Figure 6), where point G is located between XY (green). In the GRM, the minimum XY occurs when the two receivers are located exactly at point G. As the receivers move apart, the angle between XH and YH at point H changes. The objective is to find the XY distance where the bisector angle between XH and YH equals the critical refraction angle. By plotting the Offset-AG values against the calculated T_v values for different XY , we can identify the XY for which the linear regression value is closest to 1. This is selected as the optimal XY , and it will be used in subsequent calculations to determine T_G . From the T_v -Offset-AG graph, the slope of the line gives the apparent velocity of the second layer (V'), which is then used to calculate \bar{V} (Figure 7).

Figure 6: The figure illustrates the process of determining the optimal XY distance for velocity analysis.

According to Figure 7, with the optimal XY and V' , the next step is to calculate T_G using the equation (8).

$$T_G = \frac{T_{AY} + T_{BX} - T_{AB} - \left(\frac{XY}{V'}\right)}{2} \quad (8)$$

Once T_G and V' are determined, the T_G -Offset diagram can be plotted, which will ultimately confirm the selection of the optimal XY , consistent with the T_G -Offset diagram at $XY = 10 \text{ m}$ (Figure 8).

Figure 7: The figure illustrates the T_v -Offset-AG graph.

Figure 8: The figure illustrates the T_G -Offset-AG graph.

With the optimal T_G , V' , and XY values obtained from the velocity analysis, the \bar{V} value is calculated using the equation (9). Finally, using these parameters, the thickness of the first layer beneath each geophone can be determined using the equation 10:

$$\bar{V} = \sqrt{\frac{V'^2 XY}{XY + 2T_G V'}} \quad (9)$$

$$h = \frac{T_G \bar{V} V'}{\sqrt{V'^2 - \bar{V}^2}} \quad (10)$$

With the coordinates of each geophone, a cross-section of the subsurface can be generated, providing the actual geometry of the refracting surface (Figure 9).

Figure 9: : The figure illustrates the cross section of GRM.

3- CONCLUSTIONS

Numerical results of the application of three mentioned methods on the South Thomson Project's dataset demonstrate that the Generalized Reciprocal Method (GRM) provides more accurate subsurface imaging than the delay-time and plus-minus methods by effectively addressing complex geological features such as dipping layers and lateral velocity variations. GRM's reciprocal time calculations enable better depth and velocity estimations, offering a more precise image of the subsurface. This precision makes it superior in seismic refraction interpretation, particularly in areas with irregular or faulted structures, where the other methods struggle with accuracy.

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